

Isocyanide Reactions Toward the Synthesis of 3-(Oxazol-5-yl)Quinoline-2-Carboxamides and 5-(2-Tosylquinolin-3-yl)Oxazole

Zahra Yasaei, Zeinab Mohammadpour, Morteza Shiri*, Zahra Tanbakouchian and Shima Fazelzadeh

Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Physics and Chemistry, Alzahra University, Tehran, Iran

A palladium-catalyzed three-component reaction between 5-(2-chloroquinolin-3-yl)oxazoles, isocyanides, and water to yield 3-(oxazol-5-yl)quinoline-2-carboxamides is described. Interestingly, sulfonylation occurred when the same reaction was performed with toluenesulfonylmethyl isocyanide (TosMIC) as an isocyanide source. The reaction with 5-(2-chloroquinolin-3-yl)oxazoles and TosMIC in the presence of Cs_2CO_3 in DMSO afforded 5-(2-Tosylquinolin-3-yl)oxazoles. In basic media, TosMIC probably decomposed to generate Ts^- species, which were replaced with Cl^- . Tandem oxazole formation with subsequent sulfonylation of 2-chloroquinoline-3-carbaldehydes to form directly 5-(2-tosylquinolin-3-yl)oxazoles was also investigated.

Keywords: palladium acetate, carboxamidation, isocyanides, sulfonylation, TosMIC

OPEN ACCESS

Edited by:

Jonathan G. Rudick,
Stony Brook University, United States

Reviewed by:

Steven Ballet,
Vrije University Brussel, Belgium
Zhong-zhu Chen,
Chongqing University of Arts and
Sciences, China

*Correspondence:

Morteza Shiri
mshiri@alzahra.ac.ir

Specialty section:

This article was submitted to
Organic Chemistry,
a section of the journal
Frontiers in Chemistry

Received: 03 January 2019

Accepted: 28 May 2019

Published: 14 June 2019

Citation:

Yasaei Z, Mohammadpour Z, Shiri M,
Tanbakouchian Z and Fazelzadeh S
(2019) Isocyanide Reactions Toward
the Synthesis of 3-(Oxazol-5-
yl)Quinoline-2-Carboxamides and
5-(2-Tosylquinolin-3-yl)Oxazole.
Front. Chem. 7:433.
doi: 10.3389/fchem.2019.00433

INTRODUCTION

Quinolines are heterocyclic compounds exhibiting diverse and well-documented bioactivity and physical properties as well as existing as scaffolds in complex structures of natural products (Michael, 2002; Hranjec et al., 2017). Accordingly, quinoline synthesis, and functionalization has attracted much attention from synthetic organic chemists (Marco-Contelles et al., 2009; Shiri et al., 2011; Prajapati et al., 2014; Sharma et al., 2018; Nainwal et al., 2019).

However, isocyanides play an important role in synthesizing *N*-containing heterocycles and are particularly widely applied in Ugi and Passirini reactions (Domling and Ugi, 2000; Domling, 2006). Amides are especially valuable as precursors in synthesizing of bioactive and natural structures, in medicinal chemistry as well as protein synthesis (Bode, 2006; Rönn et al., 2008).

Many natural products such as urukthapelstatin A have been isolated from marine sources, these contains, several aminocarbonyl and oxazole functional groups with cytotoxic activity against human lung cancer (Yu et al., 2009). Similarly, venturamides A and B showed *in vitro* antimalarial activity (Linington et al., 2007; Davyt and Serra, 2010). Additionally, aerucyclamid C, a hexameric cyclopeptide, extremely active against *T. brucei rhodesiense*, which causes sleeping sickness, and exhibits lower activity against *P. falciparum*, the deadliest species of *Plasmodium*, which causes malaria (Davyt and Serra, 2010). Microcyclamide A is a cyclic hexapeptide with three five-membered heterocycles. It is isolated from cyanobacterium *M. aeruginosa*, and it has exhibited cytotoxic effects against P388 murine leukemia (Ishida et al., 2000; Davyt and Serra, 2010; Raveh et al., 2010) (Figure 1).

Classical procedures for amide bond formation include reactions between carboxylic acids and amines (Linington et al., 2007; Davyt and Serra, 2010). Another route involves reactions of acyl halides, acyl azides, acyl imidazoles, anhydrides, or esters (activated carboxylic acid species) with amines (Ulijn et al., 2002; Montalbetti and Falque, 2005). As well as classical routes for amides synthesis which have own merits and demerits, direct aminocarbonylation from aryl halides in metal-catalyzed reactions has attracted attention from chemists due to its significant advantages benzamide preparation (Åkerbladh et al., 2017). In this regard, many synthetic methods have been introduced, including copper-catalyzed reactions of aryl halides and isocyanides in DMSO (Yavari et al., 2014). A palladium-catalyzed reaction was developed for amidation of aryl halides (Jiang et al., 2011), as well as the synthesis of 4-aminophthalazin-1(2*H*)-ones in a palladium-catalyzed reaction with isocyanide insertion in a multi-component reaction, which is difficult to achieve via a classical route (Vlaar et al., 2011). Palladium-catalyzed isocyanide insertion was applied to a carboxamidation/hydroamidation reaction to synthesize isoindolin-1-one derivatives (Pathare et al., 2016). Another example is the synthesis of isoquinolin-1(2*H*)-one derivatives via a palladium-catalyzed cascade reaction from isocyanide and amides (Wang et al., 2002; Tyagi et al., 2012; Chaudhary et al., 2013). Very recently, Guan et al reported an efficient method for the synthesis of multisubstituted 1*H*-imidazo-[4,5-*c*]quinoline derivatives via sequential van Leusen/Staudinger/aza-Wittig/carbodiimide-mediated cyclization (Guan et al., 2018).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

General

The solvents and chemicals purchased from Merck and Aldrich chemical companies. Unless otherwise mentioned they used without further purification. Melting points are taken on an Electrothermal 9100 apparatus and are uncorrected. IR spectra recorded on a Shimadzu Infra-Red Spectroscopy IR-435. Nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectra recorded on a Bruker AVANCE Spectrometer (400 MHz for ^1H , 100 MHz for ^{13}C) in DMSO- d_6 and CDCl_3 as solvent, TMS used as internal standard. The elemental analysis carried out with a Leco CHNS model 932. Mass spectra recorded on Agilent Technology (HP) 5973 Network Mass Selective Detector operating at an ionization potential of 70 eV.

The Typical Procedure for the Synthesis of 5-(2-chloroquinolin-3-yl)oxazole 3a

A mixture of 2-chloro-quinoline-3-carbaldehyde **2a** (191 mg, 1.0 mmol), *p*-toluenesulfonylmethyl isocyanide **1** (234 mg, 1.2 mmol) and K_2CO_3 (341 mg, 2.5 equiv.) was added to EtOH (5.0 ml) and stirred for 3.5 h, at room temperature. After completion of the reaction, monitored by TLC, the mixture poured into cool water and stirred for 30 min. The product **3a** filtered, washed with water two times and dried on the air.

The Typical Procedure for the Synthesis of N-cyclohexyl-3-(oxazol-5-yl)quinoline-2-carboxamide 5a

A mixture of 5-(2-chloroquinolin-3-yl)oxazole **3a** (230 mg, 1.0 mmol), of $\text{Pd}(\text{OAc})_2$ (11 mg, 5 mol%) and Cs_2CO_3 (325 mg,

1.0 mmol) stirred in DMSO:H₂O, 9:1 (5 mL) at 80°C for 15 min. Cyclohexyl isocyanide **4a** (120 mg, 1.1 mmol) was added and the reaction stirred for 4 h. After completion of the reaction (the progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC) organic layer was extracted by DCM, washed with brine, dried over Na₂SO₄ and its solvent evaporated on a rotary evaporator. The residue was washed with 2-propanol and recrystallized in methanol to give **5a**. It is noteworthy that **5a** and **5h** purified by washing with 2-propanol but other derivatives were purified by a column chromatography (*n*-hexan: ethyl acetate 3:1) and recrystallized in EtOH.

The Typical Procedure for the Synthesis of 5-(2-tosylquinolin-3-yl)oxazole 6a-e

A mixture of 2-chloroquinoline-3-carbaldehyde **2a** (191 mg, 1.0 mmol), *p*-toluenesulfonylmethyl isocyanide **1** (468 mg, 2.4 mmol) and Cs₂CO₃ (810 mg, equiv.) was added to DMSO (5.0 ml) and stirred for 5 h at 80°C. After completion of the reaction and monitored by TLC, the mixture poured into cool water and stirred for 30 min, then extracted with DCM. The product **6a** purified by a column chromatography (*n*-hexan: ethyl acetate 4:1).

Supplementary Material

N-Cyclohexyl-3-(oxazol-5-yl)quinolone-2-carboxamide (5a)

Copies of NMR spectra are provided as **Supplementary Materials**. White powder, mp.: 123–128°C. ¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ = 1.25–1.52 (m, 5H), 1.68–1.71 (m, 1H), 1.80–1.85 (m, 2H), 2.10–2.13 (m, 2H), 3.99–4.02 (m, 1H), 7.60 (s, 1H), 7.67 (t, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 2H), 7.82 (t, *J* = 7.8 Hz, 1H), 7.90 (d, *J* = 8.4 Hz, 1H), 8.03 (s, 1H), 8.14 (d, *J* = 8.4 Hz, 1H), 8.44 (s, 1H) ppm. ¹³C-NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃): δ = 25.0, 25.6, 33.0, 48.6, 120.4, 125.9, 127.9, 128.0, 128.6, 129.5, 131.0, 137.9, 145.9, 148.5, 148.8, 151.0, 164.3 ppm. **Mass:** *m/z* 321 (M⁺) (calcd. For C₁₉H₁₉N₃O₂: 321.37). FT-IR (KBr): ν_{max}: 1604, 3444 cm⁻¹. **Anal. calcd. for** C₁₉H₁₉N₃O₂: C, 71.01; H, 5.96; N, 13.08. Found: C, 71.10; H, 5.81; N, 13.17.

N-Cyclohexyl-8-methyl-3-(oxazol-5-yl)quinolone-2-carboxamide (5b)

White powder, mp: 181–185°C. ¹H-NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ = 1.15–1.74 (m, 10H), 2.75 (s, 3H), 3.83 (m, 1H), 7.52 (s, 1H), 7.63 (d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 1H), 7.73 (d, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 1H), 7.97 (d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 1H), 8.60 (s, 1H), 8.74 (s, 1H) ppm. ¹³C-NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ = 17.8, 25.0, 25.6, 25.8, 32.5, 33.8, 48.5, 118.6, 121.8, 125.0, 126.7, 127.6, 128.3, 131.4, 135.2, 136.9, 145.0, 147.8, 153.0, 167.0 ppm. **Mass:** *m/z* 335 (M⁺) (calcd. for C₂₀H₂₁N₃O₂: 335.40). FT-IR (KBr): ν_{max}: 1646, 2853, 2922, 3310, 3444 cm⁻¹. **Anal. calcd. for** C₂₀H₂₁N₃O₂: C, 71.62; H, 6.31; N, 12.53%. Found: C, 71.55; H, 6.47; N, 12.42%.

N-Butyl-6-methyl-3-(oxazol-5-yl)quinoline-2-carboxamide (5c)

White powder, mp: 124–127°C. ¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ = 1.01 (t, *J* = 7.2 Hz, 3H), 1.45–1.54 (m, 2H), 1.67–1.74 (m, 2H), 2.61 (s, 3H), 3.53 (dd, *J* = 13.4 Hz, *J* = 6.8 Hz, 2H), 7.60

(s, 1H), 7.65 (s, 1H), 7.68 (s, 1H), 7.77 (s, 1H), 8.03 (t, *J* = 5.2 Hz, 2H), 8.37 (s, 1H) ppm. ¹³C-NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃): δ = 13.8, 20.2, 21.8, 31.7, 39.5, 120.4, 125.7, 125.8, 126.5, 126.6, 128.1, 129.0, 133.4, 137.2, 138.9, 142.9, 150.9, 165.2 ppm. **Mass:** *m/z* 309 (M⁺) (calcd for C₁₈H₁₉N₃O₂: 309.36). FT-IR (KBr): ν_{max}: 1542, 1652, 2858, 2928, 2956, 2922, 3114, 3299 cm⁻¹. **Anal. calcd. for:** C₁₈H₁₉N₃O₂, C, 69.88; H, 6.19; N, 13.58%. Found C, 67.03; H, 6.24; N, 13.65%.

N-Cyclohexyl-6-methoxy-3-(oxazol-5-yl)quinoline-2-carboxamide (5d)

White powder, mp: 157–162°C. ¹H-NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ = 1.04–1.27 (m, 5H), 1.57–1.74 (m, 5H), 3.93 (s, 3H), 3.93 (m, 1H), 7.52 (dd, *J* = 9.2, *J* = 2.8 Hz, 1H), 7.61 (d, *J* = 2.8 Hz, 1H), 7.92 (d, *J* = 9.2 Hz, 1H), 7.96 (s, 1H), 8.71 (s, 1H), 8.77 (s, 1H) ppm. ¹³C-NMR (100 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ = 24.9, 25.8, 30.8, 31.2, 33.8, 47.9, 56.2, 106.7, 115.8, 121.3, 124.6, 127.5, 128.3, 129.6, 135.9, 142.4, 143.1, 146.5, 153.4, 158.7 ppm. **Mass:** *m/z* 351 (M⁺) (calcd. for C₂₀H₂₁N₃O₃: 351.40). FT-IR (KBr): ν_{max}: 1666, 2927, 2966, 3286, 3423 cm⁻¹. **Anal. calcd. for** C₂₀H₂₁N₃O₃: C, 68.36; H, 6.02; N, 11.96%. Found: C, 68.47; H, 6.14; N, 12.11%.

N-Cyclohexyl-3-(oxazol-5-yl)benzo[h]quinoline-2-carboxamide (5e)

White powder, mp: 224–267°C. ¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ = 1.28–1.58 (m, 6H), 1.85–1.88 (m, 2H), 2.16–2.19 (m, 2H), 4.07–4.10 (m, 1H), 7.30 (s, 1H), 7.74 (d, *J* = 2.4 Hz, 1H), 7.79–7.85 (m, 3H), 7.93 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 1H), 7.97 (d, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 1H), 8.07 (s, 1H), 8.49 (s, 1H), 9.19 (d, *J* = 7.6 Hz, 1H) ppm. ¹³C-NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃): δ = 24.9, 25.7, 29.7, 33.2, 48.5, 77.2, 121.3, 124.3, 124.7, 126.6, 126.9, 127.7, 128.2, 129.1, 130.1, 130.6, 134.1, 137.5, 144.2, 146.7, 148.5, 151.1, 164.5 ppm. **Mass:** *m/z* 371 (M⁺) (calcd for C₂₃H₂₁N₃O₂: 371.43). FT-IR (KBr): ν_{max}: 1646, 2852, 2936, 3119, 3294, 3448 cm⁻¹. **Anal. calcd. for:** C₂₃H₂₁N₃O₂, C, 74.37; H, 5.70; N, 11.31%. Found: C, 74.29; H, 5.84; N, 11.52%.

6-Chloro-N-cyclohexyl-3-(oxazol-5-yl)quinoline-2-carboxamide (5f)

White powder, mp: 226–232°C. ¹H-NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ = 1.25–1.52 (m, 5H), 1.68–1.83 (m, 3H), 2.09–2.12 (m, 2H), 3.94–4.04 (m, 1H), 7.54 (d, *J* = 8.0 Hz, 1H), 7.63 (s, 1H), 7.71 (dd, *J* = 9.0 Hz, *J* = 2.4 Hz, 1H), 7.86 (d, *J* = 2.4 Hz, 1H), 8.02 (s, 1H), 8.05 (d, *J* = 9.2 Hz, 1H), 8.34 (s, 1H) ppm. ¹³C-NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃): δ = 24.9, 25.6, 33.0, 48.7, 77.3, 121.2, 126.4, 126.6, 128.5, 131.0, 131.9, 134.5, 136.3, 144.1, 147.9, 149.0, 151.2, 164.2 ppm. **Mass:** *m/z* 355 (M⁺) (calcd. for C₁₉H₁₈ClN₃O₂: 355.82). FT-IR (KBr): ν_{max}: 663, 1649, 2852, 2923, 3279, 3443 cm⁻¹. **Anal. calcd. for:** C₁₉H₁₈ClN₃O₂, C, 64.13; H, 5.10; N, 11.81%. Found: C, 64.20; H, 5.16; N, 11.70%.

N-(tert-Butyl)-6-chloro-3-(oxazol-5-yl)quinoline-2-carboxamide (5g)

White powder, mp: 190–197°C. ¹H-NMR (400 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ = 1.43 (s, 9H), 7.75 (s, 1H), 7.86 (dd, *J* = 9.2 Hz, *J* = 2.4 Hz, 1H), 8.14 (d, *J* = 8.8 Hz, 1H), 8.28 (d, *J* = 2.4 Hz, 1H), 8.46 (s, 1H), 8.64

(s, 1H), 8.76 (s, 1H) ppm. $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (100 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ = 28.8, 51.5, 119.5, 125.5, 127.4, 128.3, 131.3, 131.8, 132.7, 133.8, 144.5, 147.4, 153.4, 167.1 ppm. **Mass:** m/z 329.78 (M^+) (calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2$: 329.09). FT-IR (KBr): ν_{max} : 1626, 2852, 2928, 3334, 3423 cm^{-1} . Anal. calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{16}\text{ClN}_3\text{O}_2$: C, 61.91; H, 4.89; N, 12.74. Found: C, 62.04; H, 4.95; N, 12.89.

N-(tert-Butyl)-3-(oxazol-5-yl)quinolone-2-carboxamide (5h)

White powder, mp: 102–106°C. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ = 1.43 (s, 9H), 7.56 (s, 1H), 7.72 (t, J = 7.4 Hz, 1H), 7.87 (t, J = 7.6 Hz, 1H), 8.13 (t, J = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 8.41 (s, 1H), 8.61 (s, 1H), 8.77 (s, 1H) ppm. $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (100 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ = 28.8, 51.4, 118.7, 125.1, 127.5, 128.4, 128.8, 129.1, 131.4, 134.7, 146.0, 147.8, 153.0, 153.1, 167.4 ppm. **Mass:** m/z 295 (M^+) (calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2$: 295.34). FT-IR (KBr): ν_{max} : 1658, 2904, 2966, 3422 cm^{-1} . **Anal. calcd.** for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_3\text{O}_2$: C, 69.14; H, 5.80; N, 14.23%. Found: C, 69.20; H, 5.87; N, 14.35%.

5-(2-Tosylquinolin-3-yl)oxazole (6a)

White powder, mp: 149–152°C. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ = 2.46 (s, 3H), 7.50 (d, J = 7.2 Hz, 2H), 7.77–7.90 (m, 6H), 8.18 (d, J = 7.6 Hz, 1H), 8.69 (s, 1H), 8.92 (s, 1H) ppm. $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (100 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ = 21.6, 118.2, 127.6, 128.2, 128.9, 129.5, 129.6, 130.1, 130.6, 132.9, 135.5, 141.1, 144.9, 145.3, 145.6, 153.4, 155.1 ppm. **Mass:** m/z 350 (M^+)

(calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{S}$: 350.39). FT-IR (KBr): ν_{max} : 683, 1073, 1103, 2851, 2920 cm^{-1} . Anal. calcd. for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{S}$: C, 65.13; H, 4.03; N, 7.99; S, 9.15%. Found: C, 65.23; H, 4.14; N, 8.06; S, 9.21%.

5-(8-Methyl-2-tosylquinolin-3-yl)oxazole (6b)

White powder, mp: 162–167°C. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ = 2.18 (s, 3H), 2.50 (s, 3H), 7.55 (d, J = 8.0 Hz, 1H), 7.71 (d, J = 6.8 Hz, 2H), 7.88 (s, 1H), 7.90 (d, J = 7.6 Hz, 2H), 8.03 (dd, J = 6.8 Hz, J = 2.8 Hz, 1H), 8.73 (s, 1H), 8.95 (s, 1H) ppm. $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (100 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ = 16.5, 21.7, 117.5, 126.6, 127.7, 128.3, 129.9, 130.1, 130.4, 132.5, 135.3, 137.4, 140.3, 143.5, 145.3, 145.5, 153.6, 153.8 ppm. **Mass:** m/z 364 (M^+) (calcd. for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{S}$: 364.42). FT-IR (KBr): ν_{max} : 1294, 1379, 2852, 2922 cm^{-1} . Anal. calcd. for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{S}$: C, 65.92; H, 4.43; N, 7.69; S, 8.80%. Found: C, 66.03; H, 4.49; N, 7.78; S, 8.93%.

5-(6-Methyl-2-tosylquinolin-3-yl)oxazole (6c)

White powder, mp: 124–127°C. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ = 2.51 (s, 3H), 2.59 (s, 3H), 7.30 (s, 1H), 7.38 (d, J = 6.4 Hz, 2H), 7.62 (d, J = 8.4 Hz, 1H), 7.68 (s, 1H), 7.84 (d, J = 8.0 Hz, 1H), 7.89 (d, J = 7.6 Hz, 2H), 8.10 (s, 1H), 8.44 (s, 1H) ppm. $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ (100 MHz, DMSO- d_6): δ = 21.6, 21.7, 118.3, 127.3, 127.5, 128.2, 129.2, 129.5, 130.0, 135.1, 135.7, 140.2, 140.8, 142.9, 143.6, 145.2, 145.7, 153.3 ppm. **Mass:** m/z 364 (M^+) (calcd. for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{S}$: 364.42). FT-IR (KBr): ν_{max} : 823, 1375, 2853, 2923 cm^{-1} . Anal. calcd. for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{S}$: C, 65.92; H, 4.43; N, 7.69; S, 8.80%. Found: C, 65.98; H, 4.49; N, 7.77; S, 8.86%.

5-(6-Methoxy-2-tosylquinolin-3-yl)oxazole (6d)

White powder, mp: 187–190°C. $^1\text{H-NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3): δ = 2.51 (s, 3H), 3.99 (s, 3H), 7.16 (d, J = 8.8 Hz, 2H), 7.30

TABLE 1 | Optimization of the reaction condition for the synthesis of N-cyclohexyl-3-(oxazol-5-yl)quinoline-2-carboxamide **5a** from **3a**.

Entry	Solvent	Base	Catalyst/Ligand	Time(h)	Yield 5a ^a (%)
1	Dioxane	Cs_2CO_3	$\text{Pd}(\text{OAc})_2/\text{PPh}_3$	8	86
2 ^c	CH_3CN	Cs_2CO_3	$\text{Pd}(\text{OAc})_2/\text{PPh}_3$	8	21
3 ^c	EtOH	Cs_2CO_3	$\text{Pd}(\text{OAc})_2/\text{PPh}_3$	8	0
4	Toluene	Cs_2CO_3	$\text{Pd}(\text{OAc})_2/\text{PPh}_3$	8	5
5	DMF	Cs_2CO_3	$\text{Pd}(\text{OAc})_2/\text{PPh}_3$	8	82
6	DMSO	Cs_2CO_3	$\text{Pd}(\text{OAc})_2/\text{PPh}_3$	6	92
7	DMSO	Cs_2CO_3	$\text{Pd}(\text{OAc})_2/-$	1.5	92
8	DMSO	Cs_2CO_3	PdCl_2	12	74
9	DMSO	Cs_2CO_3	$\text{Pd}(\text{PPh}_3)_3$	12	61
10	DMSO	Cs_2CO_3	–	12	0
11	DMSO	K_2CO_3	$\text{Pd}(\text{OAc})_2/-$	12	90
12	DMSO	NaOAc	$\text{Pd}(\text{OAc})_2/-$	12	20
13	DMSO	KO^tBu	$\text{Pd}(\text{OAc})_2/-$	12	48
14	DMSO	DABCO	$\text{Pd}(\text{OAc})_2/-$	12	5
15	DMSO	Et_3N	$\text{Pd}(\text{OAc})_2/-$	12	0

^aIsolated yields. ^bAll reactions were carried out using **3a** (1 mmol), **4a** (1.1 mmol), catalyst (5 mol %), base (1 mmol), and solvent (2.0 mL) and 80°C unless otherwise noted. ^cAt reflux.

TABLE 2 | Synthesis of various derivatives of **5a-5h**^a.

^aAll reactions were performed using **3** (1 mmol), **4** (1.1 mmol), $\text{Pd}(\text{OAc})_2$ (5 mol %), Cs_2CO_3 (1 mmol), and 0.5 mL of H_2O in 4.5 mL of DMSO and 80°C.

(s, 1H), 7.39 (s, 1H), 7.58 (d, $J = 8.8$ Hz, 2H), 7.84 (d, $J = 9.2$ Hz, 2H), 7.90 (d, $J = 8.4$ Hz, 1H), 8.10 (s, 1H), 8.42 (s, 1H) ppm. ^{13}C -NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3): $\delta = 37.1, 55.8, 104.6, 119.1, 124.0, 124.4, 124.8, 129.2, 129.6, 131.6, 135.6, 137.5, 138.4, 138.5, 144.5, 147.1, 147.6, 147.7$ ppm. Mass: m/z 380 (M^+) (calcd for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4\text{S}$: 380.42). FT-IR (KBr): ν_{max} : 1037, 117, 2850, 2920 cm^{-1} . Anal. calcd. for: $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4\text{S}$, C, 63.14; H, 4.24; N, 7.36; S, 8.43%. Found: C, 63.21; H, 4.29; N, 7.43; S, 8.55%.

5-(2-Tosylbenzo[h]quinolin-3-yl)oxazole (6e)

White powder, mp: 202–207°C. ^1H -NMR (400 MHz, CDCl_3): $\delta = 2.60$ (s, 3H), 7.30 (s, 1H), 7.52 (d, $J = 8.0$ Hz, 2H), 7.57 (t, $J = 7.2$ Hz, 1H), 7.70 (t, $J = 6.8$ Hz, 1H), 7.73 (d, $J = 8.8$ Hz, 1H), 7.89 (d, $J = 8.4$ Hz, 1H), 7.92 (d, $J = 9.2$ Hz, 1H), 8.04 (d, $J = 8.4$ Hz, 2H), 8.16 (d, $J = 5.6$ Hz, 1H), 8.20 (d, $J = 8.4$ Hz, 1H), 8.60 (s, 1H) ppm. ^{13}C -NMR (100 MHz, CDCl_3): $\delta = 21.8, 119.0, 124.1, 124.4, 127.0, 127.8, 128.0, 128.7, 129.3, 129.3, 130.2, 130.5, 131.1, 134.0, 135.3, 137.5, 134.3, 144.8, 145.5, 151.6, 153.3$ ppm. Mass: m/z 400 (M^+) (calcd for $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{S}$: 400.45). FT-IR (KBr): ν_{max} : 1313, 1400, 2853, 2920 cm^{-1} . Anal. calcd. for: $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{S}$, C, 68.98; H, 4.03; N, 7.00; S, 8.01%. Found: 69.06; H, 4.11; N, 7.12; S, 8.14%.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In continuation of our interest in quinoline chemistry (Shiri et al., 2012, 2016a, 2017a) and isocyanide reactions (Shiri et al., 2016b, 2017b; Salehi and Shiri, 2019), we began our investigation with 2-chloroquinoline-3-carbaldehyde (**1**) and its two step reaction with two different isocyanides. In the presence of K_2CO_3 , 2-chloroquinoline-3-carbaldehyde (**1**) and 4-toluenesulfonylmethyl isocyanide (TosMIC) (**2**) furnished 5-(2-chloroquinolin-3-yl)oxazole (**3a**). Several 5-(2-chloroquinolin-3-yl)oxazoles (**3**) were prepared under the same conditions. The reaction of quinoline **3a** with cyclohexyl

isocyanide **4a** was selected as a model reaction in the presence of $\text{Pd}(\text{OAc})_2$, Ph_3P , and Cs_2CO_3 , in 1,4-dioxane with a few drops of H_2O as solvent at 80 °C. Desired product **5a** was obtained in 86% yield (Table 1). Solvent screening showed that DMSO is the best solvent (Table 1, entry 6). Other Pd sources such as $\text{Pd}(\text{PPh}_3)_4$ and PdCl_2 did not improve the product yield, however, the best yield was obtained with 5 mol% of $\text{Pd}(\text{OAc})_2$ even without PPh_3 (Table 1, entries 7–9). Without palladium, the reaction did not occur (Table 1, entry 10). Moreover, the effect of base is crucial for reaction completion. Hence, different bases were investigated, including K_2CO_3 , NaOAc , $(\text{CH}_3)_3\text{OK}$, DABCO, and Et_3N (Table 1, entries 14–18). In this survey, it was found that increasing the temperatures or the reaction time decreased the product yield.

With the optimized reaction conditions in hand ($\text{Pd}(\text{OAc})_2$ (5 mol%), Cs_2CO_3 (1 equiv.), $\text{DMSO} + \text{H}_2\text{O}$ (9:1), 80°C), the generality of the reaction was explored (Table 2). A range of quinolines **3** bearing electron-donating groups, such as Me, and OMe and electron-withdrawing groups, such as Cl and benzo, reacted with cyclohexyl isocyanide and *n*-butylisocyanide to afford the corresponding 3-(oxazol-5-yl)quinoline-2-carboxamides **5a-f** in 70%–94% yields (Table 2). Moreover, the bulky *tert*-butyl isocyanide smoothly participated in this reaction to furnish **5g** and **5h** in 67 and 76% yield, respectively. The yield with 1,1,3,3-tetramethylbutyl isocyanide was too low to allow its isolation and characterization.

The scope of the reaction was explored using tosylmethyl isocyanide (TosMIC) **1** as another isocyanide source. Surprisingly, the reaction of **3a** with TosMIC under the optimized conditions afforded 5-(2-tosylquinolin-3-yl)oxazole (**6a**) (Scheme 1).

Although the reaction proceeded well without a palladium source, the presence of base is crucial. Among the bases Cs_2CO_3 , K_2CO_3 , NaOAc , *t*-BuOK, and DABCO, Cs_2CO_3 gave the best results.

SCHEME 1 | The reaction of TosMIC with **3a**.

SCHEME 2 | One-pot synthesis of 5-(6-methyl-2-tosylquinolin-3-yl)oxazole **6a**.

FIGURE 2 | 5-(2-Tosylquinolin-3-yl)oxazole **6**.

Encouraged by the tosylation results with TosMIC, we explored extending the reaction to tandem oxazole formation as well as tosylation of 2-chloroquinoline-3-carbaldehyde. Subjecting 2-chloroquinoline-3-carbaldehyde and TosMIC to the standard reaction conditions yielded 5-(2-tosylquinolin-3-yl)oxazole (**6a**) in 83% yield after 8 h (**Scheme 2**). Notably, sulfones are present in different bioactive compounds (Metzner and Thuillier, 1994; Fang et al., 2016); however, well-known sulfonylating agents include sulfonyl halides (Tocco et al., 2013; Zhang et al., 2015), sulfonyl hydrazides (Yuan et al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2018), and sodium sulfinate (Sun et al., 2017; Smith et al., 2018). A few studies used TosMIC as a sulfonyl precursor (Liu et al., 2014; Phanindrudu et al., 2016; Kadari et al., 2017). Furthermore, Bounar et al. reacted tosylmethyl isocyanide (TosMIC) with propargylic alcohols in the presence of silver acetate to efficiently yield (*E*)-vinyl sulfones (Bounar et al., 2015); this is the only study in which TosMIC plays a dual role as both an amide and a sulfonyl source.

The above cascade oxazole formation and sulfonylation strategy could be extended to other 2-chloroquinoline-3-carbaldehyde derivatives (**Figure 2**). A methyl group was tolerated on positions 6 and 8 of **2** to afford **6b** and **6c**, respectively, in 82 and 62% yields. Furthermore, quinoline **2d** reacted with TosMIC, affording **6d** in good yield. Product **6e**, existing an alternative decoration of the quinoline ring, was obtained in 85% yield.

Our proposed mechanism for the tosylation of quinoline involved *in situ* Ts⁻ generation by decomposition of *p*-toluenesulfonylmethyl-isocyanide **1** in the presence of base with subsequent aromatic nucleophilic substitution to form 2-sulfonyl quinoline **6**. Although application of TosMIC as a sulfonyl source was reported by

Liu et al. for synthesizing sulfonyl benzoheteroles, the sulfonation mechanism involved aliphatic nucleophilic substitution (Liu et al., 2014).

CONCLUSION

In summary, we have developed a synthesis of 5-(2-chloroquinolin-3-yl)oxazole via a van Leusen procedure from 2-chloroquinoline-3-carbaldehydes and TosMIC, which were efficiently subjected to Pd-catalyzed amidation with isocyanides to form 3-(oxazol-5-yl)quinoline-2-carboxamides. The synthesis of 5-(2-tosylquinolin-3-yl)oxazole via a Cs₂CO₃-mediated domino process starting from 2-chloroquinoline-3-carbaldehydes with TosMIC was also demonstrated.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

ZM, ZT, and SF synthesized all of the compounds with the help of ZY. MS supervised this work and wrote the paper with the help of ZY.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We are thankful to Alzahra University and the Iran National Science Foundation (INSF) for the financial support.

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

The Supplementary Material for this article can be found online at: <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fchem.2019.00433/full#supplementary-material>

Supplementary Data Sheet 1 | Isocyanide reactions toward the synthesis of 3-(Oxazol-5-yl)quinoline-2-carboxamides and 5-(2-Tosylquinolin-3-yl)oxazole.

REFERENCES

- Åkerbladh, L., Schembri, L. S., and Larhed, M., Odell, L. R. (2017). Palladium(0)-catalyzed carbonylative one-pot synthesis of N-acylguanidines. *J. Org. Chem.* 82, 12520–12529. doi: 10.1021/acs.joc.7b02294
- Bode, J. W. (2006). Emerging methods in amide- and peptide-bond formation. *Curr. Opin. Drug Discov. Devel.* 9, 765–775. doi: 10.1002/chin.200721229
- Boumar, H., Liu, Z., Zhang, L., Guan, X., Yang, Z., Liao, P., et al. (2015). Silver-catalyzed cascade reaction of tosylmethyl isocyanide (TosMIC) with propargylic alcohols to (*E*)-vinyl sulfones: dual roles of TosMIC. *Org. Biomol. Chem.* 13, 8723–8728. doi: 10.1039/C5OB01129A
- Chaudhary, A., Sharma, P. P., Bhardwaj, G., Jain, V., Bharatam, P. V., Shrivastav, B., et al. (2013). Synthesis, biological evaluation, and molecular modeling studies of novel heterocyclic compounds as anti-proliferative agents. *Med. Chem. Res.* 22, 5654–5669. doi: 10.1007/s00044-013-0556-x
- Davy, D., and Serra, G. (2010). Thiazole and oxazole alkaloids: isolation and synthesis. *Mar. Drugs* 8, 2755–2780. doi: 10.3390/md8112755
- Domling, A. (2006). Recent developments in isocyanide based multicomponent reactions in applied chemistry. *Chem. Rev.* 106, 17–89. doi: 10.1021/cr0505728
- Domling, A., and Ugi, I. (2000). Multicomponent reactions with isocyanides. *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 39, 3168–3210. doi: 10.1002/1521-3773(20000915)39:18<3168::AID-ANIE3168>3.0.CO;2-U
- Fang, Y., Luo, Z., and Xu, X. (2016). Recent advances in the synthesis of vinyl sulfones. *RSC Adv.* 6, 59661–59676. doi: 10.1039/c6ra10731a
- Guan, Z.-R., Liu, Z.-M., and Ding, M. W. (2018). New efficient synthesis of 1H-imidazo-[4,5-*c*]quinolines by a sequential Van Leusen/Staudinger/aza-Wittig/carbodiimide-mediated cyclization. *Tetrahedron* 74, 7186–7192. doi: 10.1016/j.tet.2018.10.052
- Hranjec, M., Horak, E., Babic, D., Plavljanić, S., Srdović, Z., Steinberg, I. M., et al. (2017). Fluorescent benzimidazo[1,2-*a*]quinolines: synthesis, spectroscopic and computational studies of protonation equilibria and metal ion sensitivity. *N. J. Chem.* 41, 358–371. doi: 10.1039/c6nj02268e
- Ishida, K., Nakagawa, H., and Murakami, M. (2000). Microcyclamide, a cytotoxic cyclic hexapeptide from the *Cyanobacterium microcystis aeruginosa*. *J. Nat. Prod.* 63, 1315–1317. doi: 10.1021/np000159p
- Jiang, H., Liu, B., Li, Y., Wang, A., and Huang, H. (2011). Synthesis of Amides via palladium-catalyzed amidation of aryl halides. *Org. Lett.* 13, 1028–1031. doi: 10.1021/ol103081y
- Kadari, L., Palakodety, R. K., and Yallapragada, L. P. (2017). Electrochemical decarboxylative sulfonylation of cinnamic acids with aromatic sulfonylhydrazides to vinyl sulfones. *Org. Lett.* 19, 2580–9661. doi: 10.1021/acs.joc.7b01741
- Linington, R. G., González, J., Ureña, L., Romero, L. I., Ortega-Barria, E., and Gerwick, W. H. (2007). Venturamides, A and B: antimalarial constituents of the panamanian marine cyanobacterium *Oscillatoria* sp. *J. Nat. Prod.* 70, 397–401. doi: 10.1021/np0605790
- Liu, J., Liu, Z., Liao, P., and Bi, X. (2014). Modular synthesis of sulfonyl benzoheteroles by silver-catalyzed heteroaromatization of propargylic alcohols with *p*-toluenesulfonylmethyl isocyanide (TosMIC): dual roles of TosMIC. *Org. Lett.* 16, 6204–6207. doi: 10.1021/ol5031316
- Marco-Contelles, J., Perez-Mayoral, E., Samadi, A., Carreiras, M. D., and Soriano, E. (2009). Recent advances in the Friedländer reaction. *Chem. Rev.* 109, 2652–2671. doi: 10.1021/cr800482c
- Metzner, P., and Thuillier, A. (1994). *Sulfur Reagents in Organic Synthesis*. Best synthetic methods. eds A. R. Katritzky, O. Meth-Cohn, and C. W. Rees (London: Academic Press).
- Michael, J. P. (2002). Quinoline, quinazoline and acridone alkaloids. *Nat. Prod. Rep.* 19, 742–760. doi: 10.1039/B104971M
- Montalbetti, C. A. G. N., and Falque, V. (2005). Amide bond formation and peptide coupling. *Tetrahedron* 61, 10827–10852. doi: 10.1016/j.tet.2005.08.031
- Nainwal, L. M., Tasneem, S., Akhtar, W., Verma, G., Khan, M. F., Parvez, S., et al. (2019). Green recipes to quinoline: a review. *Eur. J. Med. Chem.* 164, 121–170. doi: 10.1016/j.ejmech.2018.11.026
- Pathare, R. S., Sharma, S., Elagandhula, S., Saini, V., Sawant, D. M., Yadav, M., et al. (2016). Application of isocyanides as amide surrogates in the synthesis of diverse isoindolin-1-one derivatives via a palladium-catalyzed tandem carbonylation/hydroamidation reaction. *Eur. J. Org. Chem.* 2016, 5579–5587. doi: 10.1002/ejoc.201600999
- Phanindrudu, M., Tiwari, D. K., Sridhar, B., Likhar, P. R., and Tiwari, D. K. (2016). Magnetically separable nano-copper catalyzed unprecedented stereoselective synthesis of *E*-vinyl sulfones from tosylmethyl isocyanide and alkynes: TosMIC as a source of the sulfonyl group. *Org. Chem. Front.* 3, 795–798. doi: 10.1039/C6QO00063K
- Prajapati, S. M., Patel, K. D., Vekariya, R. H., Panchal, S. N., and Patel, H. D. (2014). Recent advances in the synthesis of quinolines: a review. *Rsc Adv.* 4, 24463–24476. doi: 10.1039/c4ra01814a
- Raveh, A., Moshe, S., Evron, Z., Flescher, E., and Carmeli, S. (2010). Novel thiazole and oxazole containing cyclic hexapeptides from a waterbloom of the *Cyanobacterium microcystis* sp. *Tetrahedron* 66, 2705–2712. doi: 10.1016/j.tet.2010.02.008
- Rönn, R., Lampa, A., Peterson, S. D., Gossas, T., Åkerblom, E., Danielson, U. H., et al. (2008). Hepatitis C virus NS3 protease inhibitors comprising a novel aromatic P₁ moiety. *Bioorg. Med. Chem.* 16, 2955–2967. doi: 10.1016/j.bmc.2007.12.041
- Salehi, P., and Shiri, M. (2019). Palladium-catalyzed regioselective synthesis of 3-(hetero)arylpropynamides from *gem*-dibromoalkenes and isocyanides. *Adv. Synth. Catal.* 361, 118–125. doi: 10.1002/adsc.201800963
- Sharma, R., Kour, P., and Kumar, A. (2018). A review on transition-metal mediated synthesis of quinolines. *J. Chem. Sci.* 130:73. doi: 10.1007/s12039-018-1466-8
- Shiri, M., Faghihi, Z., Oskouei, H. A., Heravi, M. M., Fazelzadeh, S., and Notash, B. (2016a). The synthesis of iminothiophenone-fused quinolines and evaluation of their serendipitous reactions. *RSC Adv.* 6:92235. doi: 10.1039/c6ra11469e
- Shiri, M., Heydari, M., and Zadsirjan, V. (2017b). Efficient synthesis of novel functionalized pyrazolo-pyranoquinoline and tetrahydrodibenzo-[1,8]naphthyridinone derivatives. *Tetrahedron* 73,2116–2122. doi: 10.1016/j.tet.2017.02.064
- Shiri, M., Pourabed, R., Zadsirjan, V., and Sodagar, E. (2016b). Highly selective organocatalytic three-component reaction of 2-chloroquinoline-3-carbaldehydes, 6-aminouracils, and cyclic methylene active compounds. *Tetrahedron Lett.* 57, 5435–5438. doi: 10.1016/j.tetlet.2016.10.057
- Shiri, M., Ranjbar, M., Yasaei, Z., Zamanian, F., and Notash, B. (2017a). Palladium-catalyzed tandem reaction of 2-chloroquinoline-3-carbaldehydes and isocyanides. *Org. Biomol. Chem.* 15:10073. doi: 10.1039/c7ob02043k
- Shiri, M., Zolfigol, M. A., Kruger, H. G., and Tanbakouchian, Z. (2011). Friedländer annulation in the synthesis of azaheterocyclic compounds. *Adv. Heterocycl. Chem.* 185, 139–227. doi: 10.1016/B978-0-12-385464-3.00002-9
- Shiri, M., Zolfigol, M. A., Pirveysian, M., Ayazi-Nasrabadi, R., Kruger, H. G., Naicker, T., et al. (2012). A new and facile access to the 2-(indol-3-yl)-3-nitroquinolines based on Friedländer annulations. *Tetrahedron* 68, 6059–6064. doi: 10.1016/j.tet.2012.05.006
- Smith, J. D., Ansari, T. N., Andersson, M. P., Yadagiri, D., Ibrahim, F., Liang, S., et al. (2018). Micelle-enabled clean and selective sulfonylation of polyfluoroarenes in water under mild conditions. *Green Chem.* 20, 1784–1790. doi: 10.1039/C7GC03514D
- Sun, Y., Abdulkader, A., Lu, D., Zhang, H., and Liu, C. (2017). Synthesis of (*E*)- β -iodo vinylsulfones via iodine-promoted iododisulfonylation of alkynes with sodium sulfinate in an aqueous medium at room temperature. *Green Chem.* 19, 1255–1258. doi: 10.1039/C6GC03387C
- Tocco, G., Begala, M., Esposito, F., Caboni, P., Cannas, V., and Tramontano, E. (2013). ZnO-mediated regioselective *C*-arylsulfonylation of indoles: a facile solvent-free synthesis of 2- and 3-sulfonylindoles and preliminary evaluation of their activity against drug-resistant mutant HIV-1 reverse transcriptases (RTs). *Tetrahedron Lett.* 54, 6237–6241. doi: 10.1016/j.tetlet.2013.09.017
- Tyagi, V., Khan, S., Giri, A., Gauniyal, H. M., Sridhar, B., and Chauhan, P. M. S. (2012). A ligand-free Pd-catalyzed cascade reaction: an access to the highly diverse isoquinolin-1(2*H*)-one derivatives via isocyanide and Ugi-MCR synthesized amide precursors. *Org. Lett.* 14, 3126–3129. doi: 10.1021/ol301131s
- Ulijn, R. V., Moore, B. D., Janssen, A. E. M., and Halling, P. J. (2002). A single aqueous reference equilibrium constant for amide synthesis–hydrolysis. *J. Chem. Soc. Perkin Trans. 2* 1024–1028. doi: 10.1039/B108041E

- Vlaar, T., Ruijter, E., Znabet, A., Janssen, E., de Kanter, F. J. J., Maes, B. U. W., et al. (2011). Palladium-catalyzed synthesis of 4-aminophthalazin-1(2H)-ones by isocyanide insertion. *Org. Lett.* 13, 6496–6499. doi: 10.1021/ol202784d
- Wang, L., Woods, K. W., Li, Q., Barr, K. J., McCroskey, R. W., Hannick, S. M., et al. (2002). Potent, orally active heterocycle-based combretastatin A-4 analogues: synthesis, structure–activity relationship, pharmacokinetics, and *in vivo* antitumor activity evaluation. *J. Med. Chem.* 45, 1697–1711. doi: 10.1021/jm010523x
- Yavari, I., Ghazanfarpour-Darjani, M., and Bayat, M. J. (2014). Synthesis of amides via copper-catalyzed amidation of aryl halides using isocyanides. *Tetrahedron Lett.* 55, 4981–4982. doi: 10.1016/j.tetlet.2014.05.032
- Yu, L.-L., Li, Z. -Y., Peng, C. -S., Li, Z. -Y., and Guo, Y. -W. (2009). Neobacillamide, A., a novel thiazole-containing alkaloid from the marine bacterium *Bacillus vallismortis* C89, associated with south China sea sponge *Dysidea avara*. *Helv. Chim. Acta* 92, 607–612. doi: 10.1002/hlca.200800349
- Yuan, Y., Yu, Y., Qiao, J., Liu, P., Yu, B., Zhang, W., et al. (2018). Exogenous-oxidant-free electrochemical oxidative C–H sulfonylation of arenes/heteroarenes with hydrogen evolution. *Chem. Commun.* 54, 11471–11474. doi: 10.1039/C8CC06451B
- Zhang, D., Cui, X., Zhang, Q., and Wu, Y. (2015). Pd-Catalyzed direct C–H bond sulfonylation of azobenzenes with arylsulfonyl chlorides. *J. Org. Chem.* 80, 1517–1522. doi: 10.1021/jo502451k
- Zhang, J., Wang, Z., Chen, L., Liu, Y., Liu, P., and Dai, B. (2018). The fast and efficient KI/H₂O₂ mediated 2- sulfonylation of indoles and N-methylpyrrole in water. *RSC Adv.* 8, 41651–41656. doi: 10.1039/c8ra09367a

Conflict of Interest Statement: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Copyright © 2019 Yasaei, Mohammadpour, Shiri, Tanbakouchian and Fazelzadeh. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (CC BY). The use, distribution or reproduction in other forums is permitted, provided the original author(s) and the copyright owner(s) are credited and that the original publication in this journal is cited, in accordance with accepted academic practice. No use, distribution or reproduction is permitted which does not comply with these terms.